

The following Brief Scientific Policy Information, also available in french language, is produced as part of the component **“High Seas, Remote and/or Deep Seabed [HS/RS/DS] & Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction [ABNJ]” & WIO N.O.I.S.E.** (a multi-disciplinary network of researchers on Western Indian Ocean National Or International SEamounts, banks, submarine structures) of the DIDEM Project¹.

WESTERN
INDIAN
OCEAN
NATIONAL
OR
INTERNATIONAL
SEAMOUNTS, BANKS & SUBMARINE STRUCTURES

Multi-disciplinary network of researchers on Western Indian Ocean National or International SEamounts, banks & submarine structures
Réseau pluridisciplinaire de chercheurs sur les monts sous-marins, bancs, plateaux & autres structures sous-marines nationales et internationales

DIDEM

Dialogue Science-Decision Makers for Integrated Management of Coastal and Marine Environment

CONTACT : florence.galletti@ird.fr | jean-francois.ternon@ird.fr
UMR MARBEC | MARine Biodiversity, Exploitation and Conservation | www.umd-marbec.fr

FAIR Management of marine data in the Western Indian Ocean Remote areas and in Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction (ABNJs) to inform multilateral strategies and actions

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13819928>

Author : Julien BARDE

julien.barde@ird.fr

1. Keywords

Marine data, FAIR, Indian Ocean, Nairobi Convention, DOI, Data Management Plans, Sharing, ABNJ

2. Definition of terms

FAIR data means that data are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable;

DOI means digital object identifier(DOI), DOI is a persistent identifier or handle used to uniquely identify various objects, standardized by the International Organization for Standardization (ISO). They are widely used to identify academic, professional, and government information, such as journal articles, research reports, data sets, and official publications (source: Wikipedia);

ABNJ or Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction» means the “high seas”, and “the Area” as the seabed and ocean floor and subsoil thereof.

3. Introduction

This Brief Scientific Policy Information focuses on good practices for scientific data management (FAIR principles), blocking points & incentives for the implementation of such practices in the context of ABNJs, examples of ABNJs data FAIRly shared and ongoing initiatives in the WIO and concludes with the need for Data Managements Plans.

4. Historical context of the question, including current context

Open and reproducible science becomes a key issue for the whole society. Scientific data, information and knowledge are indeed expected to facilitate the process of decision and policy making. In particular, access (open or restricted) to literature, along with related data and code is critical to foster research by ensuring that research objects won't be lost beyond the lifetime of research projects and that research work can be reproduced and reused by other scientists worldwide. This is particularly critical for the marine domain and open ocean where data collection is challenging and costly. This has been said for years, however, data sharing among scientists has still to be drastically improved. This highlights the strong limitations of a bottom up approach, a situation that can be fixed by decision makers with strong incentives on the data policy of funding agencies as well as scientific organisations.

5. Scientific and/or governance issues raised

In this context, over the past years, funding agencies, research organisations, scientific journals are increasingly asking scientists to define strategies and implement Data Management Plans (DMP) complying with FAIR data principles to ensure that data and research objects funded by the citizens will be well managed and can be reused in the long term (e.g. by assigning DOIs). Global warming makes this

¹IRD PROJET DIDEM « Dialogue Science-Decision-Makers for the Integrated Management of the Coastal and Marine Environment” - Integrating scientific knowledge into decision-making for coastal and marine management in the Western Indian Ocean 2021-2024 » / component “High Seas, Remote and/or Deep Seabed [HS/RS/DS] & Areas beyond National Jurisdiction [ABNJ]” & WIO N.O.I.S.E./, is supported by IRD, FFEM and Société des Explorations de Monaco, with the Nairobi Convention for the Protection, Management and Development of the Marine and Coastal Environment of the Western Indian Ocean Region (Nairobi Convention) as a partner.

www.didem-project.org | <https://www.didem-project-en.org/12/high-sea>

FONDS FRANÇAIS POUR
L'ENVIRONNEMENT MONDIAL

point a hot topic worldwide and it is well known that blocking issues are human while technical solutions are already mature.

Understanding what are the main concepts, the good practices and the key stakeholders to enable the FAIR management of marine data is a first challenge for most researchers who prefer to focus on writing scientific articles (to boost their own career) rather than spending time sharing data which will benefit other colleagues. Faced with the urgency of the e.g. climate change, pandemics and ecological crisis it might be risky to wait for researchers to be trained and convinced in order to finally take the time required to implement the main principles of open science.

6. Issues and experiences in other oceans or seas

This is the reason why, unfortunately, coercive measures by funding agencies have proved to be the most effective way to make a good step forward by making Data Management Plans mandatory and agreeing that costs to implement such plans are eligible on the budget of the projects (e.g. EU H2020 research projects). Indeed, once Data Management Plans have become mandatory for projects and have been duly provided to answer the calls, the second challenge for projects, when funded, consists in gathering the technical skills (human, software and hardware components) needed to implement these Data Management Plans and supply a network of international data infrastructures. FAIR data management can't be achieved without will, budget and incentives. In the marine domain, more than others are wasted if only used by the very few researchers involved in the data collection process.

7. Useful scientific governance steps undertaken or to be undertaken in the WIO

Multiple organisations, projects and initiatives already deal with these issues in the marine science domain in the Western Indian Ocean area and work on defining strategies (e.g. Nairobi Convention). However, data sharing can not no longer be on a goodwill basis and a better coordination of existing activities and initiatives is required which implies gathering a network of stakeholders interested in these topics or directly involved in FAIR management of marine data in the WIO area.

While action needs thus to be taken urgently for data not to be lost (the FAIR management of future projects has to be enforced by policy and the legacy of data funded by past projects has to be rescued), there is still a need to foster interactions and partnerships with more advanced regions to discuss and define the vision of what the regional network of data managers and related initiatives in the WIO area should be. This will help to refine and adopt a regional strategy by promoting a set of good practices for FAIR data management which are already implemented in other regions. There is thus a clear will from the society at a global scale and simple and efficient ways have already been identified by policy makers to define both a legal framework and capacity building network which will help scientists to endorse and implement the principles of a FAIR data management.

8. Case illustrations, training and discussion

Collecting marine data is challenging and this is obviously more difficult for sampling areas which are far from the coast, especially in ABNJs. If

the distance to coast is not an issue for satellite data, this is a real challenge for collecting *in situ* data. In any case, the economic cost and the scientific interest are too high for these data not to be shared as it is done in domains like astronomy. This is for example a key issue to measure the impact of climate change, to calibrate satellite products and ocean models. Over the years, technological improvements enable scientists to collect more and more data on physical and chemical parameters by deploying sophisticated platforms and sensors from scientific vessels. Model outputs, remote sensing data (satellite images, bathymetry...) and *in situ* observations of physical and chemical parameters are usually well managed and shared by ocean observatories worldwide.

However, physical and chemical parameters are not the only Essential Ocean Variables to be collected and shared widely. Indeed biological parameters are all the more essential as they allow scientists to assess and monitor the ecological health of these areas which are also key for biodiversity and food safety at a global scale. Unfortunately there is no solution to be expected by citizen sciences in the case of ABNJs (contrary to coastal zone areas where citizen data can be shared by using infrastructures like iNaturalist). When facing the both important needs and costs of the biological data collection effort on one side, and the intense activities of fisheries worldwide in either coastal or high seas on the other side, it becomes obvious that the main opportunity to feed science and ocean observatories with biological parameters has to come from fishing vessels.

This kind of partnership with the private sector has proven to be very efficient for other parameters like bathymetry, sea surface temperature by sharing and reusing openly the data collected by vessels of the merchant ships (equipped with new sensors when required).

Similar examples exist with fisheries data provided by fishing vessels (declarative data, onboard observers or statistics at landings). Many are however reluctant to share these data out of their country at a high spatial, temporal or even taxonomic resolution (target species being considered more important than bycatch) arguing for the strategic interest of these data either from the economic or scientific careers point of view, making these key data underused. Some fisheries data are, however, disseminated in the public domain at a lower resolution by complying with the rules of the relevant Fisheries regional organisations such as IOTC for the Indian Ocean. The FIRMS Global Tuna Atlas gives an overview of what could be achieved for all species related to fisheries activities worldwide if this data could be shared in a more efficient way. This would obviously fill the important gaps on biodiversity data availability (as illustrated by the Global Biodiversity Information Facility data portal). On the other side, public or private funding agencies like Monaco Explorations can set up scientific cruises in ABNJs where data sharing becomes mandatory for scientists to ensure that data collected will be widely disseminated and reused in the long term (by using data repositories like e.g. Zenodo).

Beyond individual interests and for the common good of shared resources they host, ABNJs management policy is also a great opportunity to adopt new measures to foster public and private sector partnership and FAIR data management that is required to better study and face climate change and biodiversity crisis.

It also aligns with the changes required from States and organisations by the Agreement under the United Nations Convention on the Law of

the Sea on the Conservation and Sustainable Use of Marine Biological Diversity of Areas beyond National Jurisdiction (BBNJ Agreement, 2023). The new practices required are intended to order 1) an increase in the general and procedural transparency of activities carried out at sea and 2) legible knowledge of these activities provided to those who have not carried them out: they are thus informed. In this way, they can express an informed opinion in legal situations where such an opinion will be required, and they can express a vote (e.g. in the COP) in situations where a vote will be required of national delegation, to rule on, among others, marine protected areas (MPA) or measures such as area-based management tools proposals in the ABNJ.

9. Recent legal texts and incentives

- **COP 11, Nairobi Convention, 2024, 20-22 August** (Regional Ocean governance Strategy and Information Management Strategy: ROGS & IMS)

«Decision CP11/7: The Information Management Strategy for the Western Indian Ocean region

1. To urge Contracting Parties to adopt and implement the Information Management Strategy for the Western Indian Ocean region.
2. To request the Secretariat to enhance the Clearing House Mechanism of the Nairobi Convention by establishing a secure, centralized database infrastructure to accommodate data and information storage and exchange at both national and regional levels.»

- **The Western Indian Ocean Information Management Strategy (IMS)**

A Western Indian Ocean Information Management Strategy (IMS) January 2024, 22 p. listed as: [UNEP_EAF_CP11_3_Annex_IVa_Draft_Western_Indian_Ocean_Regional_Information_Management_Strategy_\(IMS\)_\(2024\)_0](#):

- **COP 10, Nairobi Convention, 2021, November**

Decision CP.10/5. Ocean Governance Strategy

« (...) 3. To request the secretariat to strengthen national data centres, through capacity development on information and knowledge management, and in collaboration with partners, to develop a regional information management strategy and mechanisms to address common challenges and take informed decision-making for ocean governance”.

10. Suggested websites and web resources

- Open Science - European Commission | https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science_en
- Global Ocean Observing System | <https://gooscean.org/>
- GBIF | <https://www.gbif.org/>
- iNaturalist | <https://www.inaturalist.org/>
- DataCite | <https://datacite.org/>
- DOI | https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Digital_object_identifier
- Fisheries and Resources Monitoring System (FIRMS) | <https://firms.fao.org/firms/en>

Related slides :

- <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.13740140>